

Scale, Saliency, and Hardship: A Comparison of the IMD and Open Banking Data

Luc Wilson^{*1}, Paul A. Longley^{†1}

Department of Geography, University College London

GISRUK 2026

Summary

This paper uses Open Banking data from ~250,000 individuals to pose two questions about the IMD. Firstly, how do current conceptions of deprivation relate to direct measures of financial hardship, as measured by application rates for short term loans; and secondly, is the IMD's spatial resolution adequate to capture precarity's granular geography. We identify regional IMD variations in capturing financial precarity and very uneven distributions of financial precarity within Lower-layer Super Output Areas. These findings have important implications for the conception and measurement of the nature and extent of pockets of deprivation, and the provision of resources to address it.

KEYWORDS: IMD, Open Banking, Precarity, LSOA

1. Introduction

The Index of Multiple Deprivation (IMD) is the most widely used index of its kind in the UK (MHCLG, 2025). Its influence extends from parliamentary debates on funding allocations (House of Commons, 2025) to academic research and local authority planning decisions. The recent release of the 2025 IMD for England and Wales presents a timely opportunity for conceptual and methodological evaluation of the updates. This paper addresses two key questions: first, whether the IMD presents a sufficiently direct measure of financial hardship, and second, whether its spatial resolution adequately captures the granular geography of financial precarity. The IMD is an official measure of disadvantage that shapes resource allocation and policy, yet its composite construction raises concerns about its directness as a measure of financial hardship.

2. Data and Methodology

This paper employs Open Banking data to look directly at individuals' financial circumstances. The data are provided via the Geographic Data Service by Salad Money, a short-term loan provider and winner of "LendTech of the Year" award at the 2025 UK FinTech Awards. The data cover over 620,000 working-age adults who applied for short-term loans between 1st of April 2024 to the 21st of March 2025. Since applicants disclose their accounts across multiple banks, the data show all transactions made and therefore provide a direct window into financial circumstances and behaviours at an individual level. This is true with the caveat that cash transactions and asset wealth are immeasurable through these means. The data used in this research are available at a unit postcode level and are attributable in the GeoDS trusted research environment to Output Area. In contrast, the IMD adopts an indirect approach, relying on proxy measures and administrative data to approximate deprivation across larger Lower-layer Super Output Areas (LSOAs).

* luc.wilson.24@ucl.ac.uk

† p.longley@ucl.ac.uk

The Open Banking data reveal the complete income profile over the preceding 18-months of short-term loan applicants. For the purposes of this study, financial precarity is deemed manifest by applying for a short-term loan whilst having total income falling within the bottom 40% of all applicants. The resulting pool of 248,920 applicants used in this paper have a maximum annualised total income of ~£36,000. This figure, excluding internal transfers and duplicate transactions, includes all incoming money to any of the applicant's accounts, not just salaries. This definition acknowledges that not all short-term loan applicants necessarily experience genuine financial hardship. Some may use loans to patch temporary disconnects between income and expenditure, whilst maintaining substantial asset wealth. However, the combination of low income and applying for high-interest loans provides strong evidence of financial hardship. This focus directly prioritises low-income loan applicants, ensuring the analysis captures genuinely precarious individuals. Figure 1 shows the regional distribution of precarity under our operational definition. An acknowledged limitation of this methodology is the use of income independent of expenditure context. This approach may systematically underestimate precarity in high-cost areas, particularly London, where the cost of living is generally higher. The effects of this are not apparent in Figure 1 however, the patterns revealed offer valuable insights into the spatial distribution of those experiencing demonstrable financial precarity. Table 1 gives regional breakdowns of rates of precarity per IMD decile, where decile 1 represents the most deprived.

While Open Banking data are available for the whole UK, this paper looks only at England and Wales, matching the coverage of the IMDs updated in 2025. The analysis uses multiple spatial scales. LSOAs, which are the resolution of the IMD, are themselves aggregations of typically four or five Output Areas (OAs), the finest granularity at which census data are typically released (ONS, 2023). This paper utilises this nested geography to assess whether the LSOA scale is appropriate for representing financial precarity.

Figure 1 Regional map of rates of low-income short-term loan applications per 10,000 working age adults.

Table 1 Regional Rates of Precarious Applicants per 10,000 Working Age Adults by IMD Decile (Decile 1 is most deprived)

Region	Decile 1	Decile 2	Decile 3	Decile 4	Decile 5	Decile 6	Decile 7	Decile 8	Decile 9	Decile 10
North East	43	44	42	40	41	41	40	43	37	36
North West	39	38	37	38	39	38	39	40	38	39
Yorkshire and The Humber	38	38	38	38	39	39	36	36	36	39
East Midlands	37	35	35	33	35	38	39	37	36	38
West Midlands	35	36	36	38	39	37	37	36	37	41
East of England	36	35	37	38	37	36	37	36	36	38
London	32	31	31	30	31	33	34	35	37	38
South East	37	35	34	36	37	38	36	37	37	36
South West	37	37	38	38	38	38	36	35	36	41
Wales	40	42	40	42	40	40	38	40	38	40

3. Analysis

Figure 2 Scatter graph of application counts for England and Wales per IMD decile. N.B. Shaded area represents 95% confidence interval for displayed linear relationship

Figure 2 shows a highly linear relationship between the IMD decile a person lives in and their likelihood to experience financial precarity. This is powerful evidence in favour of the IMD's effectiveness since at scale it is a good predictor of likelihood of precarity. However, Figure 3 demonstrates the relationship is more complex at regional scales. Wales (J) in particular maintains the strong linearity between IMD ranking and rate of precarity, whilst other regions show markedly different patterns. For instance, East England (B) appears to have an approximately quadratic relationship between IMD decile and rate of precarity. These regional divergences raise concerns about whether the IMD's construction adequately accounts for geographic variation in what deprivation means and how it manifests.

The observed regional variation points to a potential weakness in the IMD's design. By creating a single composite measure from weighted combinations of crime, environmental quality, education, health, and other factors, the index assumes these dimensions combine consistently across space to produce comparable deprivation scores, although it should be noted that the English and Welsh IMDs are not harmonised. Yet the regional patterns in this analysis suggest that the relationship between IMD rankings and actual financial precarity varies considerably across the country. All such problems can be circumvented through Open Banking data which permit direct examination of people's financial circumstances.

Additionally, the IMD falls down in its spatial scale. To demonstrate this, every OA for every LSOA has been ranked from **1** to **n** where **1** is the OA with the most low-income short-term loan applicants and **n** is the OA with the least. If financial hardship were evenly distributed through each LSOA, as the IMD assumes it is, the relationship between OA rank and the cumulative frequency of loan applications would be approximately linear. Figure 4 looks at the most deprived decile and demonstrates definitively that deprivation is not linearly distributed through the OAs, per LSOA. Approximately 40% of the precariat come from the highest ranked OA where if deprivation were evenly distributed, this value would be closer to 20%. The exact same story appeared when all other IMD deciles were tested. This therefore demonstrates that aggregation to the LSOA level systematically masks true patterns of financial precarity.

The implications of this for policy and research are significant. If financial precarity concentrates in particular OAs within LSOAs, then policies targeted at the LSOA level risk down-weighting pockets of the most acute deprivation. Anecdotally this could be an LSOA containing both a struggling council estate and an affluent residential area. The aggregate IMD score may place this area in a middle decile, rendering both the acute need and relative prosperity invisible to policy makers.

Figure 3 Scatter graphs of regional distributions of loan applicants between IMD deciles: (A) North East; (B) East; (C) North West; (D) London; (E) Yorkshire and the Humber; (F) South East; (G) East Midlands; (H) South West; (I) West Midlands and (J) Wales. Shaded area identify 95% confidence intervals for displayed linear relationship.

Figure 4 Cumulative frequency of precariat incidences per OA within LSOA for IMD decile 1.

4. Implications and Directions for Further Research

These findings do not invalidate the IMD as a policy tool, but they do counsel caution in its application and interpretation. The index performs well at identifying broad gradients of deprivation across England and Wales, as evidenced by the linearity between IMD rankings and observed precarity. However, its composite nature and coarse spatial resolution limit its merit and highlights whether a higher resolution, more direct measure of financial precarity should be adopted for many research aims.

For researchers and policymakers concerned with financial precarity, this analysis suggests supplementing or indeed substituting the IMD with more direct measures where possible. Open banking

data, whilst not universally available, offer a new avenue for developing a more direct index of economic vulnerability. They are also more frequently updateable. The iterative development of a more nuanced and precise definition of financial precarity through research promises to deliver a clearer picture of the geographies of financial precarity than has previously been available.

The regional variations in the relationship between IMD and precarity warrant further investigation. Understanding why some regions show stronger alignment than others could shed light on both the geographic specificity of precarity and potential refinements to how composite indices such as the IMD are constructed.

5. Conclusion

Through the distillation of highly granular secure geographic bank transaction data for a quarter of a million UK residents, this paper has drawn the following conclusions about the IMD. Firstly, it remains a valuable resource for representing spatial inequality, but it should not be regarded as fact. Secondly, while this analysis demonstrates that whilst the IMD successfully captures broad patterns of deprivation, it operates at a spatial scale too coarse to reliably represent financial hardships. Furthermore, its composite nature means it imperfectly measures financial precarity specifically. Direct financial data, where available, offer a more transparent and targeted assessment of economic vulnerability.

6. Acknowledgements

This work is co-funded by the ESRC and Salad Money under the GeoDS grant: ES/Z504464/1.

References

House of Commons (2025) *Indices of Deprivation: England - Hansard - UK Parliament*. Available at: <https://hansard.parliament.uk/commons/2025-12-18/debates/9F873B3A-2672-432E-B3FC-94547D701603/IndicesOfDeprivationEngland> (Accessed: 7 January 2026).

MHCLG, M. of H., Communities, and Local Government (2025) *English indices of deprivation 2025, GOV.UK*. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/english-indices-of-deprivation-2025> (Accessed: 4 January 2026).

ONS (2023) *Area type definitions Census 2021 - Office for National Statistics*. Available at: <https://www.ons.gov.uk/census/census2021dictionary/areatypedefinitions#lower-layer-super-output-areas-lsoas> (Accessed: 9 November 2025).

Biographies

Luc Wilson is a PhD candidate at UCL in the field of geographic data science, co-funded by the UBEL DTP and Salad Money. His research focuses on using Open Banking Data to understand financial precarity in the UK and its geography.

Paul A. Longley is a Professor of Geographic Information Science at UCL and Director of the Geographic Data Service at UCL. His research focuses on the application of geographic information science, with a strong emphasis on the development and deployment of geo-temporal data infrastructures developed from Big or Open Data.